

THE BLENDED LEARNING-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MANAGEMENT ON COACHING STRATEGIES IN BASKETBALL COURSE FOR PHYSICAL EDUCATION STUDENTS OF THAILAND NATIONAL SPORTS UNIVERSITY

¹WATCHARA PETCLAI, ²ARPHAT TIAOTRAKUL, ³WASANA KUNA-APISIT and ⁴KAJORNSAK ROONPRAPUNTA

Abstract

This research aims to study the management of blended learning in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students, Thailand National Sports University. The researchers collected data and performed the statistical analysis. The results of the basic data analysis of the respondents of the National Sports University student group. Of the 410 people, the majority were male, 59.76 percent were in fourth grade, and 66.10 percent were at the Sukhothai campus. 8.54 per cent have managed to learn in basketball coaching tactics courses over the past one year. The following categories are organized as follows: 31.95% on-line teaching activities, 22.47% of regular classroom activities, 22.47% of mixed learning activities. 19.74% organized on-site teaching activities 19.01%, ON-HAND activities 2.86%, ON-AIR activities 2.08% and ON-DEMAND activities 1.82%. And the effect of the level of feedback on integrated learning management conditions in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students. The National University of Sport is at the highest level. The average is 4.18, the standard deviation is 0.65. On a case-by-case basis, it was found that the objective side has an average of 4.19, the standard deviation is 0.66, the content side has an average of 4.17, the standard deviation is 0.69, the learning management activity side has an average of 4.19, the standard deviation is 0.68, the learning management media side is 0.68. It has an average of 4.18, a standard deviation of 0.72, and a measurement and evaluation aspect of learning management. It has an average of 4.17, a standard deviation of 0.74.

Keyword: Learning Management / Blended / Basketball Coaching Tactics Course

Introduction

Sport is vital to improving the quality of life of citizens and the nation. In addition, sports can be used to improve the quality of human resources physically, mentally, emotionally, socially and intellectually. Countries around the world often rely on the process of sport to create a sense of living, morality, discipline and responsibility (Department of Physical Education, 2009). It also cultivates sportsmanship, knowing how to lose, knowing how to win, knowing forgiveness, and respecting the rights of oneself and others. Create values, create pride and reconciliation of the people of the nation, which will lead to effective urban, social and economic development. According to His Majesty the King Bhumibol Adulyadej, "Sport is of great importance for the life of each person and the life of the city." Recognizing the importance of sports in improving the quality of life of human resources in the country, the Thai government has created a national sports development plan aiming to make sports an important part of the way of life, encouraging people of all sectors to be sportsmanly considerate and have a good quality of life, both physically and mentally (Bongkoch Chansukwong, 2019). The

National University of Sports is a higher education institution focused on specialized education in physical education, health, based on the philosophy of "Physical Education and Sports, People Development, National Development". One of its missions is to produce graduates and develop sports science personnel with the goal of developing knowledge, ability to become an instructor, becoming an athletic trainer, becoming a sports referee, learning skills in the 21 century, and high-level career competencies. It has been included in the Basketball Coaching Tactics Course in the Bachelor of Education program in Physical Education. The Faculty of Education 2020 is a course that is in the elective major section. Course descriptions are specified in the course to guide instructors in designing course specifications to provide instruction in the course description (M.C.3) of the course. However, due to the current teaching and learning experience, transfer expertise of the national sports university physical education instructors, there are differences in the course specification in terms of purpose, content, learning activities, learning materials, measurement and evaluation of learning outcomes. As a researcher, he is responsible for the basketball coaching tactics course and is involved in the teaching and learning. Recognizing its importance, it is interested to study "The Blended Learning-Based Instructional Management on Coaching Strategies in Basketball Course for Physical Education students of Thailand National Sports University".

Objectives of Research

This research aims to study the management of blended learning in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students, Thailand National Sports University.

Research Methodology

1. Research papers at home and abroad on learning management in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students.
2. Physical Education Students National Sports University passed a basketball coaching course, 410 people
3. Learn how to develop basketball coaches for physical education students. The National University of Sport studies the following components:
 1. Purpose
 2. Contents
 3. Learning Management
 4. Learning Materials
 5. Learning Measurement and Evaluation

Findings

The study at this stage is a study of the conditions of integrated learning management in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students. The national Sports University as follows:

1. Questionnaire results of integrated learning management in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students. National Sports University

The findings concluded that respondents to the National Sports University student group. Of the 410 people, the majority were male, 59.76 percent were in fourth grade, and 66.10 percent were at the Sukhothai campus. 8.54 per cent and Suphanburi Campus. 8.54 per cent have managed to learn in basketball coaching tactics courses over the past one year. The following categories are organized as follows: 31.95% on-line teaching activities, 22.47% of regular classroom activities, 22.47% of mixed learning activities. 19.74% organized on-site teaching activities 19.01%, ON-HAND activities 2.86%, ON-AIR activities 2.08% and ON-DEMAND activities 1.82%.

2. Feedback levels of integrated learning management in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students. National Sports University

The questionnaire consists of 5 aspects as follows: 1) Purpose 2) Content 3) Learning management 4) Learning materials 5) Learning measurement and evaluation are characterized by a rating scale defined as 5 levels of Likert's summated rating scale. 50 items as follows:

Table 1: shows the mean and standard deviations (on purpose)

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
1) Purpose			
1. It encourages learners to learn on their own. Able to research basketball rules	4.31	0.73	high
2. It encourages learners to repeat lessons they don't understand multiple times, resulting in basic basketball skills.	4.16	0.72	high
3. It encourages learners to develop critical thinking, giving rise to the attributes of being a basketball coach.	4.21	0.79	high
4. It has encouraged learners to gain confidence, resulting in the behavior of basketball coaches.	4.20	0.77	high
5. It encourages learners to know how to connect knowledge, to develop creativity, to develop a positive attitude towards basketball coaches.	4.23	0.77	high
6. It has encouraged diverse learners using modern technology to build knowledge of sports science.	4.12	0.89	high
7. It has encouraged learners to do systematic practices, enabling them to teach and practice basketball skills.	4.20	0.81	high
8. It has encouraged active learners to develop their ability to practice on basketball teams.	4.20	0.79	high
9. It has encouraged learners to do practices, report on their ability to collect, and test basketball players.	4.13	0.80	high
10. It encourages learners to complete project practices, manage and prepare strategies before and during competitions.	4.11	0.86	high
Total	4.19	0.66	high

Based on Table 1, the results of the analysis of the level of feedback of mixed learning management conditions in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students. The National University of Athletics, which has taken basketball coaching tactics courses over the past one year on purpose, has a total average of 4.19, a total standard deviation of 0.66, at a high level.

Table 2: shows the mean and standard deviations (content)

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
2) Contents			
11. Learning is provided to learners about the basics of coaching and basketball rules.	4.26	0.77	high
12. Learning is provided to learners about sports science for basketball.	4.09	0.88	high
13. Learning is organized for learners about the principles of preparing a basketball team.	4.16	0.80	high
14. Learning is organized for learners about basketball scouting.	4.11	0.82	high
15. Learning is provided to learners about organizing basketball training programs.	4.14	0.88	high
16. Learning is organized for learners about building physical fitness for basketball athletes.	4.16	0.80	high
17. Learning is organized for learners about the teaching principles and techniques of basketball skills training.	4.24	0.79	high
18. Learning is organized for learners on how to practice playing basketball teams.	4.26	0.78	high
19. Learning is organized for learners about introverting and testing basketball players.	4.09	0.81	high
20. Learning is provided to learners about managing and preparing strategies before and during the competition.	4.16	0.83	high
Total	4.17	0.69	high

According to Table 2, the level of content commentary analysis had a total average of 4.17, a total standard deviation of 0.69.

Table 3: shows the average and standard deviations (learning management activities)

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
3) Learning Management Activities			
21. Organize learning activities that focus on learners in the right sequence of steps, able to have an understanding of basketball coaches.	4.24	0.81	high
22. Organize learning activities that encourage students to study for themselves from various media and learning resources. Able to develop students' basketball coaching skills.	4.18	0.79	high
23. Organize learning activities, each coordinated, flexible time can enhance the attributes of being a basketball coach.	4.12	0.80	high
24. Organize learning activities that can be exchanged for both face-to-face and online learning to develop students' basketball teaching skills.	4.15	0.86	high
25. Organize learning activities with both regular classroom methods combined with online instruction that develops basketball coaching skills to suit the learner's skill level.	4.17	0.81	high
26. Organizing learning activities encourages learners to be active and can encourage students to take pride in the basketball coaching profession.	4.15	0.81	high
27. Organizing learning activities with peers in the classroom can encourage learners to demonstrate committed, active, and empathetic behavior in their duties as a basketball coach.	4.24	0.79	high
28. Organize online learning activities that benefit learners in terms of access to information, encouraging learners to practice their basketball coaching skills with intention.	4.22	0.83	high
29. Learning activities encourage learners to research lessons at any time, at any location, according to their potential for online learning, along with face-to-face learning, allowing them to practice their basketball coaching skills with fun.	4.22	0.77	high
30. Organize learning activities to practice skills using information technology so that learners can develop up-to-date information search skills and build their own knowledge.	4.22	0.79	high
Total	4.19	0.68	high

According to Table 3, the results of the analysis of the level of feedback on learning management activities had a total average of 4.19, the total standard deviation of 0.68 was at a considerable level.

Table 4: shows the average and standard deviations (media aspects of learning management)

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
4) Media Learning Management			
31. Learning materials are consistent with many forms of learning activities.	4.24	0.83	high
32. Choose from a variety of interesting media and learning resources in line with the content.	4.22	0.83	high
33. The proper use of media and technology or innovation in teaching to promote learning for learners.	4.23	0.79	high
34. The application of electronic materials in online learning is combined with face-to-face instructional materials in the classroom to enhance teaching and learning efficiency.	4.21	0.83	high
35. Learners are engaged in the independent selection of technological materials for learning under the supervision of the instructor.	4.19	0.82	high
36. Have the right and adequate technology and internet system.	4.09	0.92	high
37. Put article content on the web through online electronic media for collaborative learning activities.	4.19	0.86	high
38. There are innovative materials related to information. Information technology has undergone changes that are appropriate in line with the practice of learning management.	4.17	0.86	high
39. Innovative materials are used to model learning situations to encourage active learners to pay attention.	4.10	0.91	high
40. Modern learning materials are used to facilitate and facilitate students.	4.12	0.90	high
Total	4.18	0.72	high

From Table 4, the results of the analysis of the level of media comments, learning management. It has a total average of 4.18, a total standard deviation of 0.72 is at a high level.

Table 5: shows the average and standard deviations (measuring and evaluating learning management)

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
5) Measuring and evaluating learning management			
41. Create comprehensive and comprehensive student measurement and evaluation tools that are fully aligned with defined learning objectives.	4.16	0.85	high
42. There are methods for measuring and evaluating basketball coach knowledge that are appropriate for learners.	4.18	0.86	high
43. There are criteria for measuring and evaluating basketball coaching skills that are appropriate for learners.	4.23	0.86	high
44. There are criteria for measuring and evaluating attitudes towards being the right basketball coach for students.	4.22	0.81	high

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
45. Learning outcomes are measured and evaluated in accordance with the learning management activities provided to learners.	4.12	0.86	high
46. Learning outcomes are measured and evaluated, providing feedback to contribute to self-improvement.	4.09	0.90	high
47. It provides opportunities for learners to participate in evaluating the work of both themselves and their roommates to encourage them to know themselves, believe themselves, and develop information.	4.20	0.85	high
48. Clearly define the criteria for evaluating learners' learning management.	4.16	0.85	high
49. Measuring and evaluating learning outcomes, learners' ability to transfer learning into real life.	4.16	0.84	high
50. Measuring and evaluating results achieves the learning objectives of being a basketball coach.	4.15	0.86	high
Total	4.17	0.74	high

According to Table 5, the level of analysis of the level of feedback on measurement and evaluation of learning management had a total average of 4.17, a total standard deviation of 0.74 at higher level.

Table 6: Summary shows the average and standard deviations of integrated learning management in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students, national sports universities, who have taken basketball-coaching courses in the past one year

List	Comment Level		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret the Results
1) Purpose	4.19	0.66	high
2) Contents	4.17	0.69	high
3) Learning Management Activities	4.19	0.68	high
4) Media Learning Management	4.18	0.72	high
5) Measuring and evaluating learning management	4.17	0.74	high
Total	4.18	0.65	high

From Table 6, the results of the analysis of the level of feedback of integrated learning management in the development of basketball coaches for physical education students. National Sports University, which has been studying basketball coaching tactics for the past 1 year. When considering the five aspects, it was found that the objective side has an average of 4.19, the standard deviation is 0.66. Contents It has an average of 4.17, a standard deviation of 0.69. Learning Management Activities, it has an average of 4.19, the standard deviation is 0.68. The media side of learning management has an average of 4.18, a standard deviation of 0.72, and a learning management measurement and evaluation side. It has an average of 4.17, a standard deviation of 0.74.

Discussion

The Blended Learning-Based Instructional Management on Coaching Strategies in Basketball Course for Physical Education students of the Thailand National Sports University, the importance is very high. It can be explained that blended learning is a flexible approach. Can support location synchronization and coupled with an integrated or integrated learning environment as a combination of classroom teaching, both teachers and students need to be empowered to encourage more effective teaching and learning. In line with Pongsathorn Paijit (2018), the need for physical education teachers, should have four areas that are needed to enhance the competencies of physical education students: research and development of physical education learning, physical education measurement and evaluation, physical education learning management, and classroom management. And the main characteristics of blended learning, it is an integrated approach between regular classroom instruction and collaborative learning activities through online electronic media. It allows learners to work as a team and responsibly, to control their own learning through a learning environment in which each lesson is placed on a CD-ROM and prepared through a network system, with communication between learners and instructors or learners and learners. Others using E-mail and group conversations. According to Zhang Yingjie and Wang Wen (2020), the evaluation of the basketball curriculum's blended learning in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes has been accepted by students for blended learning, i.e., a combination of instruction from two historically separate teaching styles: traditional face-to-face learning systems and online learning systems.

Recommendations for implementing the findings

1. The Ministry of Education could use the findings as a guideline for developing a basketball lesson plan to be more effective.
2. Integrated learning arrangements for basketball coaching strategies for physical education students This will benefit the instructors to use it as a way to manage learning to develop basketball coaches for physical education students who are suitable for the current situation and in the same direction.

Reference

1. Allen, Elaine & Seaman, Jeff. (2010). Learning on Demand: Online Education in the Basic Skill Learning in Basketball Students in the First Class in Faculty of Physical Education at Zagazig University. *Journal of Applied Sports Science* June, 6(2), (pp. 44-49). www.jass.alexu.edu.eg
2. Basketball Courses in Universities: Analysis of Knowledge, Skill and Attitude. 2018 Seventh International Conference of Educational Innovation through Technology (EITT) 139 -142.
3. Bongkoch Chansukwong. (2019). Sports Management Model for Excellence in Sports Schools affiliated to the National University of Sports, Kralong Tourism and Sports.
4. CAC.)2012(. Coaching code of ethics principles and ethical standards.]On-line[. Available: 2021, Retrieved December 17, from <http://www.coachesofcanada.com/files/Code of Ethics.pdf>.
5. Department of Physical Education. (2009). Trainer training courses. Bangkok: Agricultural Cooperative Assembly Printing House of Thailand. Limit.
6. Face-to-Face, and Blended Instruction. *Dissertation Abstract International*, 121(3), 209(B).
7. Formulation. Management and implementation of the 2005 curriculum reform in selected disadvantaged districts. Scotland: University of Glasgow.

8. Hany Ahmed Ahmed Abd El-Aal. (2016). Effect of Blended E-Learning Program on
9. Horn, B.M. & Staker, H. (2011) The Rise of K-12 Blended Learning.
10. Kopweh, P. S. (2014). Curriculum development in Tanzania: an investigation of the
11. Martens, R. (2012). Successful coaching (4 the Ed). Illinois: Human Kinetics.
12. Mobile App Supported Basketball Teaching: A Blended Learning Approach. 2018 Seventh International Conference of Educational Innovation through Technology (EITT) 162-165.
13. Percy, Agnes Goz. (2010). Finding the Perfect Blend: a Comparative Study of Online,
14. Pongsathorn Pajit (2018). Developing a pre-practice curriculum for teacher professional experience to strengthen the competence of teacher students in physical education. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University.
15. Presence and satisfaction in a blended learning environment: Relationships and critical factors. Computers and Education, 51, 318-336.
16. So, H-J. & Brush, T. A. (2008) Student perceptions of collaborative learning, social
17. Sriramatr, S. (2014). Physical Activities for Wellness. Chulalongkorn University. [In Thai] United States, 2009. USA: Sloan Consortium. Unpublished Paper: Innosight Institute.
18. Zhang Yingjie & Wang Wen. (2020). Student Evaluation of Blended Learning for
19. Zhang Yingjie, Wang Yuping, & Cheng Jiangang. (2018). The Design and Evaluation of